

GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA: HOW THE YOUTHS CAN GET INVOLVED

A call to action for Youth Participation in Nigerian Governance

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About the Author

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He has written several articles in various areas of life, many of which were published online and have earned accolades, rewards, and certifications.

In 2017, his NYSC essay submission to the Bible Society of Nigeria (BSN), which was centred on the “INCORRUPTIBLE JUDICIARY AS A CATALYST FOR AN EQUITABLE AND PROGRESSIVE SOCIETY” made it to the best six nationwide.

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He desires to continuously be involved in research and creative writings, so as to create positive impacts that contribute to the finding of lasting solutions that pacify the enormous problems of mankind, for a better tomorrow and a peaceful co-existence.

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ABSTRACT

According to demographic reports, Nigeria is home to an enormous youthful population, aged 18 to 35, numbering approximately 60 million. However, when discussing the fundamentals of Nigerian governance, it becomes evident that youth involvement is nearly absent or inconsequential. This paper argues that the role of youth in governance is irreplaceable, drawing upon data from local and international research, as well as personal experiences. It examines why today's youth have failed to become tomorrow's leaders. It has been discovered that youth involvement in governance faces numerous obstacles, ranging from the youth's struggle to break free from the influence of political godfathers to the lack of youth empowerment amid widespread unemployment. This is further compounded by the decay in Nigerian governance, stemming from corrupt practices, insecurity, gerontocracy, gender inequality, and more. The rise of disenchanted youth is unstoppable. Therefore, for the nation to succeed, Nigerian youths must be given the opportunity to steer the ship of governance in the right direction, as it is of great generational importance. This paper also aligns with the awakening of youth consciousness and elucidates how the youth can become involved in governance for a prosperous Nigeria.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page no
Cover Page	
About The Author- - - - -	i
Abstract- -- - - -	ii
Table Of Contents- - - - -	iii
➤ LEADERSHIP, GOVERNANCE, THE CONSTITUTION, GOVERNMENT AND YOUTHS- - - - -	1
➤ GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA: THE RISE OF EMBITTERED YOUTHS -	2
➤ OBSTACLES STOPPING YOUTH’S INVOLVEMENT IN GOVERNANCE-	5
➤ HOW THE YOUTHS CAN INVOLVE IN GOVERNANCE AND ITS EFFECT-	6
CONCLUSION - - - - -	8
BIBLIOGRAPHY - - - - -	8
Figure(s)	
Youth population (Nigerian population commission) - - - - -	-6

GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA: HOW THE YOUTHS CAN GET INVOLVED

To the Youths, “*The height of your accomplishments will equal the depth of your convictions.*” – William F. Scolavino

LEADERSHIP, GOVERNANCE, THE CONSTITUTION, GOVERNMENT AND YOUTHS

Leadership is the function of a leader who directs the people because he or she knows the way, goes the way, and shows the way. Leadership and governance work *pari passu*. **Governance** is the exercise of power by political leaders for the liberty and societal well-being of their subjects. The **Constitution** is the framework of governance. The constitution is the supreme law of the land, which gives strategic direction to leaders and also upholds the notion that individual inputs are of great importance to the achievement of good governance.

By and large, the history of governance is quite enormous and can only be summarised by understanding that governance systems arose as different societies evolved from a nomadic existence to a more settled civilization. The advent of civilization modified the ruling class and they were called the government. The **Government** are formal institutions through which a group of people are governed. Gradually, the laser beams of civilization destroyed the notion that **leadership, governance, the constitution, and the government** must run only on the sole prerogative of the older generation, thereby giving hope and opportunity to the **Youths** (young men and women) who are qualified to involve in governance and assume the mantle of leadership.

The government became an indispensable entity that executes the will, purpose, and objectives of the people. From time immemorial, several forms of government (monarchy, democracy, republican, communism, etc.) arose simultaneously with different systems of government (unitary, federal, confederate), and every sovereign state adopted the form and system of government that supports their continuous advancement as a people.

Nigeria is the most populated country in Africa and the seventh most populated country in the world; probably one of the reasons why it is called the *Giant of Africa*. It has a land area of 910,770 km² and houses a population of above 200 million people (United Nations data, 2019). Nigeria moved through different stages of political development, from **Parliamentary democracy** (1960-1966) to **Military rule** (1966-1979) and (1985-1999), and then finally to the current **Federal Republican** form of government where leaders emerge through **Democracy** (Republican-Democracy (1979-1985) and (1999 – present)).

According to Abraham Lincoln, “*Democracy is the government of the people, by the people and for the people.*” During elections, Nigerians elect representatives as Presidents, Governors, and Legislators who handle the affairs of the nation on their behalf. However, when the continuum of national leadership and growth was taken into full consideration, it was discovered that the youths of today are the leaders of tomorrow. One may ask: *who is a youth?* The definition of youth varies in connection to certain circumstances surrounding states and the diverse nature of organizational ideologies. From a layman’s perspective, a youth would be described as a person between childhood and adulthood, who is switching from the dependence of childhood to adulthood independence.

The United Nations defined youth as a person between the age range of 15 - 24 years and wisely allowed for the modification of the definition by member states. This was because of the challenging political, economic, and socio-cultural differences amongst member states. Nigeria’s National Youth Policy (2009) defines youth as a person between the age ranges of 18 - 35 years. This definition appears to be more accommodating than the views of the United Nations; the reason is because of the delay in transition to adulthood independence in Nigeria and most African countries. Due to the high rate of unemployment that cripples the youths, only a few youths in Nigeria can gain full-independence at the age of 24.

GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA: THE RISE OF EMBITTERED YOUTHS

During the colonial era, it was young Nigerians who championed the struggle for independence. Since 1960 when Nigeria gained independence till date, there has been severe violence (*in the form of five successful military coups, a civil war, continuous Boko haram and Fulani herdsmen attacks*), poor economic and resource management, youth neglect, and a distorted system of wealth distribution.

The chronicles of Nigerian governance presents a nation that has witnessed; the brief good deeds of a selected few who never lasted long enough in power to build a great nation, the rejection of eligible candidates who would build the nation, and the prolonged stay in power of many political wolves that devour the national

cake and never cared about building the nation. Repeatedly, during electioneering periods, the citizens keep desiring and reciting the features of ideal governance that include: accountability, transparency, responsiveness, equitability, inclusiveness, efficiency, respect for the rule of law etc.

But they often get deceived by the peanuts selfishly given by rich politicians. Consequently, they end up selling their conscience and they vote for candidates who clinch unto power and become respectable political parasites, who milk the national resources and treasury dry. This vicious political cycle catalyzed the rise of embittered Nigerian youths who now roam the streets to unleash mayhem. Unfortunately, these inefficient leaders often become so affluent that they become way above the law, which now only applies to the poor.

The nation becomes guilty of having a constitution without the spirit of constitutionalism. And the edict, "*All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others*" as stated by the Pigs who dominated the government in George Orwell *Animal Farm* becomes a reality. Amoral politicians are not prosecuted for crimes but are allowed to metamorphose into Godfathers (The Cabal), who use their political powers to intimidate the radically minded youth. In frustration, the youths swear clandestine oaths and end up slaving for them, instead of serving the citizens upon their assumption of any public offices. At this juncture, the Nigerian governance system is deficient of the sense of responsibility, in the sense that both the electorate and the elected leaders have failed to live up to expectation by not helping each other to strike a balance that eliminates rooms for inefficient governance.

Nigerian governance is bedeviled by endemic corruption. According to Patricia Garcia, a Peruvian physician, "*Corruption is the abuse of entrusted power for private gains.*" Corruption can be described as the ugly cankerworm that has eaten deep into the fabrics of the nation. Some people think that corruption is just something that sits in an air-

conditioned office, wears a hat, rides expensive cars, and has an office called corruption. Alarmingly, corruption has travelled beyond sophisticated offices to the dirty streets of slums, it is just as malignant as cancer, and it has metastasized at an alarming rate into every nook and cranny of the nation.

The citizens are no longer at ease. The need for “*transparency education,*” as one of the treatment plans against corruption is indispensable. It must be administered to both the old and the young, who are now fallen captives of infamous corruption. Retrospectively, the presence of corruption in the Nigerian government must surely not be the dreams of the likes of Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe, Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, and Chief Obafemi Awolowo, the founding fathers.

In essence, corruption has put a knife on the ethical principles that once held the nation together. Corruption insists that the labours of the heroes past must be in vain; and thus, the nation is falling apart. Unfortunately, only a few youths have a voice in Nigerian governance, and they mostly belong to two major categories: the Thugs and Princlings. Many youths in Nigerian politics today have made their way into political limelight by serving as efficient thugs for political Godfathers. They are adopted by politicians to execute political misconduct. They engage in crude arguments with heightened tendencies for war.

A youth’s thug-life may begin by being a vocal and violent student of school political unions. On the other hand, the princelings do not need a Godfather because they already have parents who are rooted in the corridors of political power. They venture into politics as a youth because they were born into families with strong political backgrounds. Youths who cannot live a thug life and were not born into affluent families with a strong political background view venturing into politics as almost a mission impossible.

Gerontocracy and Gender inequality are very evident in the Nigerian governance system. There is profound gerontocracy in Nigerian democracy. A Gerontocracy is a form of oligarchical rule in which the nation is presided over by elderly men and women who are much older than the rest of the adult population. The active practice of gerontocracy in democracy has pigeonholed the youths and hindered them from active involvement in governance. Gender inequality in Nigerian democracy is prevalent as men were considered superhuman to women. Women were caged to be best suited to stay at home as housekeepers. This primitive ideology has attacked the nation's developmental milestones; because they forgot that the hand that rocks the cradle rules the world.

Many professional youths have deserted the country to foreign lands in search of greener pastures, causing a brain drain because fatherland is in absolute disarray. But still, amid the ebbs and flows of Nigerian democracy, the future hope of Nigerian governance rests on the broad shoulders of the youths.

OBSTACLES STOPPING YOUTHS INVOLVEMENT IN GOVERNANCE

Abreast of the facts above, certain obstacles truly hinder the youth's involvement in governance. To begin, when the youths fail to invest in themselves, they end up with weak mental strength. Investing in oneself involves making small, continual improvements that enable one to do more and advance further. The criterion for electing a youth by society is not dependent on age alone. The society also considers the competence, character, compassion, and courage of the youth. Therefore, the youth can improve themselves by reading self-help books, acquiring skills, attending seminars, saving money, and breaking bad habits, among other strategies.

Moreover, the overbearing presence of Godfathers, coupled with the heightened apathy between the elders and the youths, has made most youths lose hope and confidence in their ability to get involved. It is a well-known fact that political offices in Nigeria cannot be occupied by mere individuals who have no connection with the Godfathers. Many desperate youths turned into political thugs and got killed during violent activities. To overcome these issues, the youths must demand a transparent government where the rule of law is evident, and the elders are willing to understand that the youths are not asking for their forceful retirement but are rightfully demanding their entitlements and mentorship.

Additionally, the presence of political apathy in the youths is caused by the remembrance of past corrupt practices, anti-politics childhood orientation, such as the ideology that politics is a dirty game, the belief that votes do not count, religious fanaticism, cynicism, and pessimism, and politicophobia, among other factors. The youths must believe that they can make a difference.

Furthermore, the sit-tight nature of leaders who desire long-term tenures drives ambitious youths away. Often these leaders discourage the youths by saying, "the youths have been unable to handle their own needs, how then would they handle the needs of the nation?" The fixing of compulsory retirement age for political leaders will pave the way for the youths.

In addition, the public perception of politics as evil and a game of pigs discourages the youth. Most Nigerian lower and middle-class parents would never agree to sponsor their children to study political science at the university, and any child that declares early interests in politics is called a black sheep. Appropriate sensitization to make people understand that leadership is servitude would be a great relief to the youths.

Moreover, the lack of youth empowerment, unemployment, and poverty are the greatest obstacles to youth involvement in governance. This is because the monetary cost of politics in Nigeria is enormous. If only the youths can be empowered and employed, they would have the zeal to engage in good governance, as a hungry man is the bridegroom of corruption.

Next, the failure of the educational and social institutions has caused more harm than good. Individuals arise from families, and families form communities, while communities create the institutions, such as schools. Failure at the family and institutional levels to produce better youths will hinder the future leadership of the nation. Thus, if families can train good children, and social institutions can polish these children into vibrant youths, the future of the nation is secured.

Finally, the reluctance of political parties to project the youths, even after the signing into law of the "Not Too Young to Run" bill by President Muhammadu Buhari's administration, is a great obstacle. The political parties serve as the training grounds for political leaders. If they can recruit the youths, encourage them, and incorporate them into the party's structure, the youths would push the nation to greater heights.

HOW THE YOUTHS CAN INVOLVE IN GOVERNANCE AND ITS EFFECT

According to Eleanor Roosevelt a former first lady of the United States, “*When one ceases to contribute, one begins to die.*” Pericles, an Athenian statesman, unequivocally stated, “*Just because you do not take an interest in politics doesn’t mean politics won’t take interest in you.*” Proverbially speaking, *the hand of the child cannot reach the shelf, and the hand of the adult cannot get through the neck of the gourd.* Thus, both the old and the young need each other for efficient governance. By default, every Nigerian youth is positioned for leadership; and the relevance of youth’s involvement in governance is to pave the way, for the continuum of governance *ad infinitum*.

The youths are the keys of Innovation irrespective of their imperfections; thus, becoming a great leader does not mean becoming a perfect human. The ugly state of governance in Nigeria may have erected a scary barricade that induces the youths to hibernate and go into a state of inexistence, which promotes minimal participation in governance. But that should not be allowed because, generational roles have propelled countries from low-income to high-income nations, as seen in Japan, Singapore, Malaysia, Brazil, etc.

Figure 1:
Source: National population commission of Nigeria

Fortunately, young people represent the largest demography in Nigeria (about 70%), out of which approximately 32% is between the age range of 18 and 35 years. A critical observation of the registered voter statistics shows that 67% of voters are the youths, which is equivalent to approximately 60 million of the Nigerian population. Directly, this infers that if the youths should actively participate in electioneering processes, whomever they chose to support has a high chance of winning.

Imaginatively, if 60 million youths were to form a country they would represent the population of the 23rd country in the world which is **Italy**, they would be called the 5th largest country in Africa which is **South Africa**, and they can be said to be twice the size of **Ghana**. To inspire the Nigerian youths, some remarkable and historical examples of youthful leaders includes; **Alexander the Great**, who conquered the known world by the age of 23. **Mhairi Black** was elected as United Kingdom Member of Parliament, at the age of 20. **Proscovia Allen Oromait** was elected as Ugandan Member of Parliament, at the age of 19. **Anyim Pius Anyim**, became Nigeria's senate president, at the age of 39. History remembers them.

Certainly, the youths can get involved in Nigerian governance in various ways. To begin, the youths must declare interest in politics (to govern the people) and begin by doing their best in their respective small capacities at the grass-root level.

Additionally, the youths must be active participants in electioneering processes; they should not sell their votes and must consistently stand with the truth.

Furthermore, the youths should be supportive and avoid being rebellious against the sitting government. They must adopt nonviolent measures to express their displeasure, such as embarking on peaceful protests, and should be law-abiding citizens rather than societal miscreants. It is crucial for them to commend the government when it performs well.

Moreover, the youths should be agents of change, thinking outside the box to generate ideas that will uplift the nation. In times like this, Nigeria needs more technologically inclined youths to adopt the e-voting platform. In addition, the youths must be open to career advancement through continuous education, as today's readers become tomorrow's leaders. They should disengage from political thuggery by aligning with reputable political leaders to eradicate political violence.

Furthermore, the youths should join reputable political parties that consider them as active stakeholders in political processes. Once part of these political parties, youths must be humble and willing to handle the tasks given to them with diligence. In time, they will meet the right people who will support them to contribute more to society.

Lastly, the youths must always speak as one in the face of adversity and stand together in solidarity for the appropriate application of the rule of law. In essence, the youths must challenge corruption. Ultimately, the combined effect of youth involvement in governance will lead to the unstoppable birth of a prosperous nation.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the youths are the eagle's eyes through which the future is seen because the future belongs to them. According to Amartya Sen, an Indian economist, "*Any economic growth without investment in human development is unsustainable and unethical.*" A wise government must believe in youth investment because "*human investment*" is the greatest of all investments. Indeed, it is true that the governance system in Nigeria is in gross jeopardy, but all hope is not lost. If one can look keenly into the eyes of the youths, hope is seen in copious amounts. When youth's involvement in governance is promoted. When the youths are encouraged to think out of the box. When the older generation brings their unalloyed support and mentorship. Nigeria, the sleeping giant will arise to walk tall again.

Contributors

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